

DOSTOEVSKY'S TRADITIONS IN THE ENGLISH LITERATURE OF FIRST HALF OF XX CENTURY (J.POWYS, J.CONRAD, J.GALSWORTHY)

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Abstract

Article is devoted research of Dostoevsky's creativity in the English literature of first half of XX century, also are analyzed Dostoevsky's traditions in creativity of English writers. The article is devoted to the study of Dostoevsky's work in English literature in the first half of the 20th century. The article also examines the traditions of Dostoevsky in the works of English writers. Dostoevsky is not just a famous writer, but also a brilliant thinker, a researcher of the human soul. Dostoevsky's heroes seek justice everywhere and in everything. They lead heated political and philosophical disputes, reflect on "being" and "nothing", express their opinion with complete frankness, with a variety of convictions, with a variety of life experiences. The heroes of the writer are always not in static, but in dynamics, in action. This is a distinctive feature in the artistic depiction of Dostoevsky.

Dostoevsky's novels are distinguished by a special style. They do not have a clear sky, a beautiful landscape, nature. There is only a human, a human voice. There are many human voices in his novels. They stand on a par with the author and always speak in an affirmative tone. In fact, Dostoevsky is the creator of a new novel genre that does not obey any laws. M.M. Bakhtin calls it a "polyphonic novel".

Each of Dostoevsky's heroes, unlike the others, is driven by his own truth, his own principles. The clash of different ideas and beliefs allows the author to find the truth, which can be the right idea for humanity. In the inner world of his characters there is a special drama. They want to resolve the age-old questions of good and evil. Their scope of thought and feeling is unlimited.

The work of the great Russian writer F.M. Dostoevsky has always been studied with special interest not only in Russia, but also in Europe. Among them are literary critics, and psychologists, and philosophers. Dostoevsky's works helped to take a different look at the world and open up its new face. The fundamental questions of life have always been resolved in novels with the participation of its heroes.

F. M. Dostoevsky is a world-class writer. He shook the whole world with his grandiose novels. His role is great not only in literature, but also in science. It was thanks to him that scientists made scientific discoveries.

Keywords: Dostoevsky, England, Literature, Tradition.

English literature of the 20th century is characterized by a great variety of artistic methods and values. It is in the 20th century that a strong desire arises for the liberation of culture and literature from the essence of Victorian society. Criticism became the dominant factor at the beginning of the 20th century. It had various forms. One of them is modernism.

Critics and historians wanted to characterize the first half of the 20th century in terms of modernism. Representatives of this movement aspired to the "new", denying the old traditions of previous generations. They completely rejected their predecessors. The spiritual crisis experienced by the intelligentsia in Great Britain at the beginning of the 20th century put realist traditions to the test. In the person of Lawrence, Joyce, Eliot, Woolf, modernism successfully developed. Their goal was to express the "inexpressible", the slightest movements of the soul, to create an atmosphere of individual life.

The ways of development of the English novel were largely determined by the artistic "discoveries" of Russian writers – I. Turgenev, L. Tolstoy, F. Dostoevsky. The role of Dostoevsky in the ideological development of the English novel is especially great. He seemed to foresee the future of mankind, like a prophet. British critics saw in him a mystic, a seer, an irrationalist. He brought a new novel genre to world literature. The theme of "underground", "duality", depth psychology so stunned English writers that they used this technique in their works.

Dostoevsky's themes – the themes of crime, sinfulness, prostitution, urban alienation, family breakdown, mental disorders, the decline of religious faith, as well as his penetrating psychological insight and prophetic understanding, modern totalitarian ideology and the socio-spiritual chaos generated by the unrest of capitalism – are deeply in tune with the demands twentieth century.

English critics called Dostoevsky's novels psychological. It is defined relatively late by English novelists as J.K. Powys and D.G. Lawrence. These writers have regarded Dostoevsky in various ways. The work of the Russian writer has become an integral part of English literature. "No English novelist has explored the human soul as deeply as Dostoevsky," noted the English novelist E.M. Forster in his book *Aspects of the Novel* (1, p. 26).

British writer and teacher J.K. Powys considered Dostoevsky "the greatest of all novelists". Powys, like his contemporaries Y. Lavrin and J. Lloyd, explored the creative path of the Russian writer. In 1915 he published a collection of articles, *Visions and Revisions; A Book of Literary Devotions*. In this collection, one article was devoted to the work of Dostoevsky. It was a small job. Then this work, like others, could be considered an important study when the First World War swept the whole of Europe. Powys compares Dostoevsky with Nietzsche in his article. According to the author, Dostoevsky saw that the impetus for the movement of life stems from the insane struggle between the "Strong" and the "Weak". Here we can agree with the

author. It was Dostoevsky's emphasis on this struggle that helped Nietzsche create his "theory" – "The Will to Power", "Superman". They converge on the "general situation", but disagree on the fact that for Nietzsche the hope for humanity lies in the "Strong", for Dostoevsky - in the "Weak". Nietzsche's aphorism: "The sick and the weak must perish, and the strongest must defeat ... Push the falling one!" And Dostoevsky says: "For the time being, I hasten to protect myself, and therefore I completely refuse the highest harmony. It is not worth the tear of even one tortured child who beat himself on the chest with his fist and prayed in his stinking kennel with his unredeemed tears to the "God"! Not worth it because his tears remained unredeemed. They must be redeemed, otherwise there can be no harmony" (2, p. 223).

According to Powys, only Dostoevsky understands the depravity of the spirit, the flesh and the amazing prank, whereby a person will not always seek his own realization and well-being, but just as often his torment and destruction. Dostoevsky really has the demonic power to reveal the dark side of the human brain, where the phantoms of unsatisfied desire hide, and where unexpressed passions stretch out miserable hands forward (3, p. 242).

The approaches of British novelists to Dostoevsky's work are different. His assessment in English criticism is measured in different ways. There is no clear relationship with him. This comes from the versatility of the novels of the Russian writer. Dostoevsky's novels are not characterized by a measured, calm flow. His element is a heightened attention to the crisis state of the individual and the world around him.

Joseph Conrad (Józef Kozheniowski) (1857-1924) was an English writer of Polish origin. Along with other English writers, he also experienced the noticeable influence of Dostoevsky. Although Conrad denied the influence of the Russian writer. Conrad, like Lawrence, "disliked" the Russian writer. This "dislike" can be explained by the fact that in the 60s of the XIX century, during the Polish liberation movement, his father was exiled to the Russian Empire – Vologda. Conrad's mother went with him after his father when he was 4 years old. The Russian Empire doomed his parents to exile and death. Hence arose alienation and hostility to Russia and its culture. In his journalism, where he deals with political issues, an anti-Russian tone is depicted. Thus appeared his political novel *Under Western Eyes* (1911), which was influenced by Dostoevsky's novel *Crime and Punishment*.

He took from the Russian writer the psychological image of the spiritual world of the hero, the transfer of his inner experience. This can be seen in his novels, especially in the novel *Through the Eyes of the West*, which reminds us of Dostoevsky's *Crime and Punishment*.

Through the Eyes of the West was written in 1911. The novel is set in Russia and Switzerland. The main character Razumov, a young, orphaned student at St. Petersburg University, has much in common with Raskolnikov. Both have similar personalities. Even the choice of a surname (Raskolnikov from "split" and

Razumov from "reason") shows that Conrad used Dostoevsky's technique. Only Razumov resembles Razumikhin, Dostoyevsky's friend, who is the embodiment of clear, practical reflection. In Dostoevsky, Razumikhin is shown with a healthy and almost cheerful attitude to the difficulties that Raskolnikov reflects on. However, Konrad gives these qualities in one person – In the person of Razumov, who, like Raskolnikov, has a "double" – Galdin. Razumov's world revolves around his relationship with his sister and mother, and so is Raskolnikov's. They both contemplate suicide while standing on the bridge. Dostoevsky, after killing the old woman, leads his hero to a confession before Sonya. Konrad, after the betrayal of his comrade, leads his hero to a confession before Natalia.

The novel *Through the Eyes of the West* is a dramatic copy of *Crime and Punishment*. Surprisingly, denying the influence of Dostoevsky, Conrad used the ways of conveying the artistic conception of the Russian novel, and thus "responded" to it in his own way. So, both writers have a similar method of conveying the "inner voice" of their characters. This is psychology.

Dostoevsky for the English writer John Galsworthy (1867-1933) was also one of these "sources". He was a supporter of realistic art, a Nobel Prize winner (1932).

Assessing the merits of Russian writers in realistic art, Galsworthy did not disregard the role of Dostoevsky in the literary process. "It is impossible to imagine," he wrote in his article, "a greater science fiction writer than Dostoevsky, and no one was able to portray the real situation so vividly" (4, p. 272).

Galsworthy, like his contemporaries (Lawrence, Conrad), was critical of Dostoevsky. Speaking about the difference between Turgenev and Dostoevsky, he called the latter an "amorphous giant" who is not a "Westernizer". Despite the fact that he considered Turgenev a "great master", from whom he learned a lot, his early novels did not remain without the influence of Dostoevsky.

In the early novels of Galsworthy, the influence of "Crime and Punishment" and "The Humiliated and Insulted" is noticeable. In the novel "First and Last" many details remind us of "Crime and Punishment". Both writers begin their work with a time factor: the time is clearly indicated at the beginning of the works. But this is not the only technique that Galsworthy inherited from the Russian writer. Larry (Lawrence) from this novel is in many ways similar to Raskolnikov. They, committing a crime, somehow want to justify themselves. Their character is the same: both Raskolnikov and Larry "do not even hurt a fly", but at the slightest injustice they raise a "revolt". Galsworthy took from Dostoevsky elements of the "subconscious" that were not characteristic of his work. So, the story with the horse, because of which Larry "was ready to kill one driver who whipped his horse mercilessly" (5, p. 43), reminds us of Raskolnikov's dream, where he experienced the same feeling in childhood. Sleep as an element of the subconscious plays an important role in the transmission of inner experiences in Dostoevsky. The Russian writer, through this dream, reveals to us the "good soul" of his hero.

After committing the crime, Larry, like Raskolnikov, does not find a place for himself. Nobody sees them at the scene of the murder. The desire to see that terrible place where the murder was committed and where the body of the murdered person lies, arises in both Raskolnikov and Larry. In both works, there is an image of a "kind girl" who, due to life's difficulties, went on a "yellow ticket". This is Sonya from "Crime and Punishment" and Wanda from "First and Last", beloved of these heroes. They play an important role in revealing the characteristics of Raskolnikov and Larry.

Larry doesn't want anyone to be judged because of him. He cannot come to terms with the fact that some old man will be executed for his murder. If Raskolnikov is waiting for hard labor in Siberia, then the hero Galsworthy commits suicide.

The German girl Mei from the novel "Defeat", who left her homeland because of the war, is in England and lives on a "yellow ticket" like Dostoevsky's heroine. She is very "suffering" like Sonya Marmeladova from "Crime and Punishment" and Natasha Ikhmeneva from "Humiliated and Insulted". With an attempt to portray a "poor" and "offended" person, Galsworthy turns to the work of Dostoevsky. May tells an English soldier who fought for his homeland about his "suffering" and "humiliated" life. The "clients" have made her life hellish and look upon her as a "fallen woman". No one wants to understand what is going on in her soul. From pain and hatred, she even hides her nationality.

The mental state of the heroine is sometimes shown by the writer as her "Russian sisters" – Sonya and Natasha.

Thus, the Russian writer Dostoevsky, having influenced the English prose of the twentieth century, thereby helped the writers to create different stylistic novel genres in the literature of Britain. He received his assessment in different ways. He was criticized and elevated to a pedestal. But, despite the different attitudes of English writers towards Dostoevsky, they repeatedly turned to his work. The writers of Britain took from the Russian writer psychologism, polyphony, the image of the "humiliated" and "offended", sinners and criminals, "fallen women", "saint" and "prostitute" in one person, elements of the "subconscious" and many others.

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